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Research Article

Self-Control Strategies for Handling Students Disruptive Behavior in the Classroom at Secondary Level

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 08-May-24 Revised: 18-June-24 Accepted: 26-June-24 Published: 30-June-24	This study was conducted to find out self-control strategies for handling student's disruptive behavior in the classroom at secondary level in Tehsil Jand District Attock. The current study was quantitative in nature and descriptive research method was used to conduct the study. The population of the study consisted of all the secondary and higher secondary school teachers. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of sample of teachers (200). A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data. It was found that teacher's self-control strategy self-understanding is helpful in handling student's disruptive behavior, teacher prepared for each activity and complete work on time and he can identify what he like or dislike.
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Introduction

The capacity to restrain one's feelings, ideas, and actions in the face of urges and temptations is known as self-control, which is a component of inhibitory control. This cognitive process, known as executive function, is essential for controlling behavior to accomplish particular objectives. What sets humans apart from the rest of the animal kingdom is our capacity for self-control, or the ability to rein in our impulses, emotions, and behaviors in order to accomplish long-term objectives. The prefrontal cortex, a considerably larger region of the brain in humans that is involved in planning, problem-solving, and decision-making, is the primary source of self-control (Sano, Sariro, & Zola, 2022).

Theoretically, having self-control is an important and "good" skill. Greater self-control allows one to put long-term objectives ahead of immediate gratification. If you're training for a marathon, for instance, making the decision to work out first thing in the morning will benefit you in the long run. However, you might be dissatisfied with your performance at the final event if you begin to oversleep and miss workouts (Tice, Bratslavsky & Baumeister, 2018).

Self-control techniques are mental and behavioral abilities people employ to stay motivated and accomplish their own objectives. Initially, a therapist, text, or self-help book may be used to teach the skills. But in order to bring about the desired changes, it is up to the individual to apply these abilities in practical settings (Converse, Juarez & Hennecke, 2019).

Classroom disruptions pose a serious threat to students' academic progress, a major source of stress for teachers, and a significant challenge to learning in schools. The behaviors of students have evolved significantly over the past 20 years, posing a serious behavioral challenge for educators in learning centers. The teacher's role in classroom management is to instill motivation and discipline as well as to get students involved in the learning process. Failure in the teaching process will occur if the teachers are unable to effectively manage their class through a variety of teaching techniques (Myers & Pianta, 2008).

Student disruptive behavior is defined as any behavior that interferes with the regular operation of a classroom, impeding learning and possibly endangering peers' and teachers' safety. This conduct can take many different forms, including talking over someone else when they are speaking, disobeying directions, frequently being late or absent, acting aggressively or defiantly, using electronics in class, and acting in a rude or distracting manner. Various underlying factors, such as personal problems, learning disabilities, attention-seeking tendencies, or a lack of engagement with the material being taught, can give rise to disruptive behavior. A balanced strategy that incorporates support, discipline, and open communication between teachers, students, and their families is necessary to address disruptive behavior in the classroom and preserve a safe and productive environment (Drane, Vernon & O'Shea, 2021).

Teachers can employ a variety of techniques to address the difficulties posed by disruptive student behavior. More effective classroom management techniques can be developed and enjoyed with the aid of adequate teaching knowledge and abilities, familiarity with pertinent and influential disciplines, and effective communication in the classroom (Herman, Prewett, Eddy, Savala & Reinke, 2020).

Review of Related Literature

Self-Control

What sets humans apart from the rest of the animal kingdom is our capacity for self-control—the ability to rein in one's impulses, emotions, and behaviors in order to accomplish long-term objectives. The planning, problem-solving, and decision-making prefrontal cortex—which is noticeably larger in humans than in other mammals—is the primary source of self-control. When it comes to creating a positive and productive learning atmosphere, a teacher's capacity for self-control is crucial. The ability of a teacher to control their feelings, responses, and behaviors in response to various classroom scenarios is referred to as self-control in the teaching context. This ability is crucial for preserving an environment that is focused and upbeat, which benefits students' academic and social growth (Schmeichel & Inzlicht, 2013).

Assessing a teacher's self-control needs to be done in a multimodal way with different kinds of information. Peer evaluations and observations in the classroom are two methods for collecting qualitative data. These data sources provide information about a teacher's temperament, capacity for emotional control, and composure in the face of difficulties or interruptions. Teachers can consider their own self-control techniques by responding to self-reported surveys and self-assessments. Students' comments, the documentation of disruptions in the classroom or disciplinary actions, or even the long-term tracking of student performance can all yield quantitative data. These data types work together to provide a thorough evaluation of a teacher's classroom self-control (Triastuti, 2020).

For a number of reasons, the self-control of a teacher is essential. It provides students with a good example by highlighting the importance of emotional control and conflict resolution. Students' social skills and self-control may then be impacted by this. A teacher who possesses self-control can better handle conflicts and disruptions in the classroom, fostering a more favorable atmosphere for learning. Self-control helps teachers stay healthy by lowering stress and burnout and, in the end, allowing them to continue being passionate and dedicated to their work. To put it briefly, self-control is not only a personal quality but also a necessary component of efficient classroom management, which in turn promotes student achievement (Domitrovich, Durlak, Staley & Weissberg, 2017).

Self-Control Strategies

"A strong defense is the best offense," as the saying goes. This is most likely true in relation to classroom management. The key to effective classroom management is prevention. Teachers are less likely to deal with problematic behavior when proactive strategies are used to carry out more preventative maintenance. However, issues will occasionally arise in even the best-run classrooms. According to some educators, the increasing "culture of disrespect" that permeates our schools is the reason why behavioral issues arise frequently, sometimes even on a daily basis. Others may not experience discipline issues very often, only in exceptional cases. But we are aware that, despite their infrequency (Morris, 2020).

Teachers need to be prepared to deal with challenging behavior when it happens in a professional and courteous manner that minimizes disruptions to the learning environment while holding offending students accountable. This is a big order, but with the reactive strategies I teach in this course, it can be accomplished in all but the most dire situations (Constantia, Christos, Glykeria, Anastasia & Aikaterini, 2023).

Appropriate action against misbehavior always starts early in the sequence of events. When behavioral issues arise, teachers must make a commitment to address them by assessing the behavior's nature or potential threat to students' learning before taking appropriate action. Although conflict is unavoidable, fighting is not. By using early intervention techniques to address misbehavior as soon as it arises, up to 90% of minor behavioral issues in the classroom can be resolved. The variety of strategies teachers employ to make sure their lesson plans are carried out smoothly and creatively with the least amount of disruptive student behavior is referred to as classroom management (Burden, 2020). Using effective classroom management techniques can make the difference between your students having a wonderful year and a miserable one. They are employing strategies to take back command in your classroom (Weinberg & Gould, 2023).

Self-Knowledge

There is no proof that kids are aware of their dual identities before they become four months old. In the second half of the first year, offspring begin to interact with toys and other objects in their environment to demonstrate personal agency. A baby's agency for knowledge emerges in her relationship with her mother after it does so with herself. Studies on spatial perception indicate that during this stage, children use themselves as landmarks to attempt to penetrate objects that they have already seen. As their second year comes to an end, the babies begin to recognize themselves. It has been observed that children gradually become more conscious of who they are as they get older. The main technique for assessing children's self-awareness who have outgrown (Eiser & van der Pligt, 2015).

Self-Regulation

In the first year of life, self-control is demonstrated. During the second year, ecology largely directs children's intended behaviors; however, in the third year, some of this control gradually shifts to the child, manifesting as self-directing speech and, eventually, as self-directing thought. The creation of self-instruction is one noteworthy achievement that denotes a shift from external environmental control to internal instruction. The frequency and complexity of using a self-control technique increase beyond the age of three. Studies on children's resistance to enticement examine common situations in which they must refrain from acting in a way that goes against their behavior. Using the forbidden toy technique, researchers have found that a number of things tend to increase one's ability to resist persuasion, including modeling, appropriate self-statements, and a strong foundation or plan for resisting restrictions. Waiting times can be influenced by self-statement and other strategies that detract from the enticing, immediately attainable rewards. As children grow older, they understand better strategies for overcoming challenges. The ability of parents to maintain fulfillment during the pre-institutional years has been correlated with their adolescent's evaluations of their cognitive, social, and imitation abilities. (Montroy, Bowles, Skibbe, McClelland, & Morrison, 2016).

Self-Acceptance

Self-acceptance is a psychological state that can result from our capacity to identify others in a logical, reasonable way through our emotional reactions and observation, thus recognizing the presence of desired behavior. The foundation of self-acceptance is accepting ourselves as we are while preserving a positive self-image. Self-acceptance or emotion, according to Bramden (1969), is an expression of who I am, even if it's not always an expression of who I like or admire at the

time it occurs. It is the understanding of reality, particularly as it relates to oneself. Branden (1969) asserted that the most crucial element of self-esteem is self-acceptance, which is also a requirement for self-esteem (Zipagan & Galvez Tan, 2023).

There are three stages involved in self-acceptance. When we first start the process of accepting who we are, we don't give up anything about who we are. Because we are human, we have judgment, behavior, and social interactions. Accepting the reflection, emotions, and metrics that our performance reveals is crucial. However, this does not imply that our approach is the only way we act, think, or feel. Angelou stated, "Now that we identify more we can do enhanced; we performed what we accomplished at the time with the information we had." After we accomplish something, we realize we can perform well because we are valuable in our capacity to perform better, according to Angelou. Being independent We are free to make the decisions we want. If we don't respect and reject ourselves, we can't truly love ourselves (Zedner, 2017).

According to Branden (1969), it is very hard for us as individuals to generate and change this lowest sagacity of self-acceptance, which results in a low regard for oneself. Being our own defender or source of strength is more crucial and essential to self-awareness. If we handle it disrespectfully, we lose all self-respect. Giving oneself value, treating oneself with respect, and standing up for one's right to survive are the first steps toward achieving self-approval and improving one's sense of self-respect. The third step to accepting oneself is to be kind to ourselves. The logic of self-approval can be established when we demonstrate that we are our own best friends. It's critical that we are truthful with ourselves. Our obligation is to If we acknowledge that we are a special and remarkable entity, then we cannot refuse to acknowledge any component. Nonetheless, we have to accept who we are based on fundamental reality rather than subjective assumptions. Recognizing our own shortcomings, we must ground our self-perception in reality rather than sentimentality. Accepting oneself for who you are does not imply contradiction. That is not to say that one should try to prove the wrong. Furthermore, what is real? It looks into the framework used to apply the accomplishment (Simonton & Garn, 2019).

Disruptive Behavior

It is deemed disruptive behavior when several transitions take place simultaneously in a similar way and the majority of students participate in them. when the transition takes too long and the instructions are unclear, giving the students nothing to do while they wait. Occasionally, disruptive behavior during a change in activity can result from an abrupt change in the activity or from a student who refuses to stop participating. Students often lose focus and fall behind when a teacher assigns the next assignment because they are not motivated or engaged in it. Disruptive behavior may also arise when the teacher modifies the lesson. When a plan increases student engagement, the amount of challenging behavior decreases (Hemmerter, Ostrosky, Artman & Kinder, 2008).

To reduce inappropriate behavior during transitional periods, it is important to establish and enforce clear class rules. Teachers and students should be well-prepared for the upcoming lesson or activity to minimize disruptions. Students should be able to quickly grasp transitional content by having easy access to it. Arranging so that school activities don't interfere with other classes can help the transition go more smoothly. Careful planning, teaching, monitoring, and feedback are necessary for a successful transition (McIntosh et al., 2004). It keeps track of how quickly the students are completing the task. During transitional times, inappropriate behavior can be minimized by creating and enforcing clear rules for the class. To reduce disruptions, teachers should thoroughly prepare their students for the upcoming lesson or activity. Easy access to

transition-related materials should enable students to comprehend them quickly. The transition can go more smoothly if arrangements are made so that school activities during other classes don't get in the way (McIntosh et al, 2004)

A smooth transition requires careful planning, three teaching, monitoring, and feedback. It is employed to monitor the speed at which the pupils complete the assignment. How well a transition proceeds depends on how teachers act, particularly during the teaching-learning process and when preparing for regular, upcoming, and ongoing tasks. When a lesson is taught with efficient time management and assignment of varied tasks, it is far more effective (Schexnailde, 2012)

Emmer and Stough (2001) argued that during the transition, the teacher moves among the students, attending to their individual needs and questions as well as helping them prepare for the next task, so minimizing disruption. A reward or other form of reinforcement can be given by the teacher to the class when they transition smoothly between activities. Students can express their creativity when there are modifications made during the teaching-learning process. Using a transition allows for an analysis of the teacher's role in social time management and allocation in the classroom. Time flow is the term for the teacher's chosen method of time management. Stated differently, the pace at which the teacher and pupils make use of the time spent in their care (Fox, 2009).

According to Johnson (2012), some students might not be aware of the effects their conversations with classmates have because they see it as a normal and non-disruptive behavior. According to Richardson (1999), educators who do not communicate to their students the appropriate and inappropriate ways to behave are more likely to have to deal with disruptive behavior in the classroom. Schneider (1998) claims that disruptive student behavior makes teachers more stressed and unhappy. He goes on to say that lecturers who expect disruptions during their lectures might start preparing for contingencies instead of focusing on lesson plans. These educators are also disheartened and disenchanting with the process of teaching and learning in the classroom (Tavakol, & Tavakoli, 2022).

Causes of student Disruptive Behavior

Waller (2008) asserts that comprehending the underlying causes of inappropriate behavior is necessary to transform it into appropriate behavior. The literature identifies a number of causes for disruptive behavior. Seidman (2005) found that misbehavior is linked to larger classes. Clayton (2000) states that when students feel like they're not being treated fairly as customers, they become disruptive. According to Axup (2008) and Shumate (2010), students' disruptive behavior is mostly caused by their need to establish their identity and get their teachers' attention. Miller, Ferguson, and Byrne (2000) claim that the main reasons why students behave disruptively are because they are vulnerable and because teachers treat them unfairly. According to Verkuyten (2002), students think that when they want to question their teachers' authority or when there isn't enough instruction, disruptive behavior happens. Emotional or physical problems may be the cause of students' disruptive behavior in the classroom. The way a classroom is set up can lead to unruly behavior in the workplace. Rudolf identified four primary reasons for the students' misbehavior. such as drawing attention, vying for dominance, getting revenge, and avoiding failure. He believed that the desire for attention is the driving force behind over 90% of misbehavior. Students who are power-hungry can cause problems for even the most experienced educators. Pupils who want to exact revenge may act disruptively; they may aim their resentment at the instructor, other students, or both (Waller, Walters, Satchell, Johnson, Daley & Reid, 2023).

Some of the more extreme student behaviors call for interventions or disciplinary actions. Higher education policies that address violent, aggressive, suicidal, and disruptive behavior incidents are impacted by the increasing proportion of students with mental health disorders in higher education. This calls into question the policies' applicability to higher education as well as the mental health of the students. Hubell (2010) enumerates a number of disruptive behaviors, including falling asleep in class while a teacher is giving a lecture, regularly arriving late, using a phone or chatting with classmates, having regular arguments with teachers, texting faculty members, being engrossed in video games, and in some cases even acting hostilely toward others. (Pecha, 2023).

Students act disruptively in the classroom when they disagree with the teacher or another student. According to O'Malley (2002), a sizable percentage of college students currently consume alcohol. According to Taylor's (2007) research, unclear expectations, a lack of transparency, deadline pressure, negative feedback, etc. frequently lead to harmful conflict between graduate students and instructors. Waller (2008) asserts that changing from inappropriate to appropriate behavior requires acknowledging one's actions. Many of the reasons why rudeness occurs these days are explained by literature. Larger class sizes are usually linked to unruly behavior from the students. Misbehavior is the result of them; students who feel they are not being treated fairly will act rudely and uncivilizedly (Wire, 2023).

One of the most frequent causes of students' disruptive behavior is their desire for their teachers' attention. Students genuinely want to be the center of attention for a particular teacher in order to define their identities. Teachers are not treating their students fairly. Consequently, one of the primary causes of students' disruptive behavior in the classroom is the injustices that the teachers do. There is a daily increase in the number of students with mental illnesses enrolled in higher education institutions. As per Richardson's (2010) findings, persistent side conversations by students in class can lead to disruptive behavior. It is very likely that disruptive behavior is a regular occurrence for students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Patnaik, & Subban, 2023).

To sleep in a classroom is truly rude. According to Kelly (2013), the teacher has a responsibility to find out why students are nodding off in class. The UNESCO Behavior Modification Module (2000) states that it is a well-established phenomenon that students who perform well on exams are more likely to exhibit symptoms of a superiority complex. Conversely, students who score poorly on exams experience feelings of inferiority. There are now a variety of non-pharmacological and psychotherapeutic methods for reducing hyperactive behavior in kids, including behavior modification techniques, parent and teacher training therapy, skill training, cognitive behavior therapy, and multi-component intervention strategies. The teaching profession is relatively new to these treatments. It is necessary to develop their senses in line with the (Larkins, 2023).

Research Objectives

1. To identify self-control strategies used by teachers in classroom at secondary school level.
2. To examine the self-control strategies used by teachers to handle students' disruptive behavior in the classroom

Research Methodology

The study was quantitative in nature and descriptive method was used to conduct the study. In descriptive method survey technique was used for the collection of data. All the secondary and higher secondary school teachers of Tehsil Jand District Attock were the population of the study. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of sample from the population. 200 teachers were selected as a sample of the study as per Gay (2009) table. The researcher developed five-point Likert scale questionnaire for the teachers to collect data from the sample of study. The questionnaire was validated from two experts of the field of education. The researcher incorporated all the suggestions made by the experts. For the purpose of pilot testing, the questionnaire was distributed among 25 secondary and higher secondary school teachers who were not the part of the final survey. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the readability, usability and reliability of the instrument. The reliability of instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha statistical technique with the help of SPSS software. The reliability of the instrument was found 0.84 which was acceptable for conducting the final survey. The researcher personally visited all the Secondary and higher secondary School teachers of Tehsil Jand District Attock and collected the data for sampled teachers. Statistical package for social science software (SPSS) was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data and interpretation of data.

Results

Table 1
Descriptive analysis of Self-understanding

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I am prepared for each activity	200	4.78
2.	I complete my work on time	200	4.26
3.	I can identify what I like and dislike	200	4.33
4.	I identify emotions in self	200	4.01
5.	I identify emotions on others	200	4.09
6.	I justify my emotions ones identified	200	4.18
7.	I empathize with those who achieve success	200	4.11
8.	I interpret body language	200	4.14
9.	I use different tone a voice to convey message	200	4.09

Table 1 presents the results self-understanding a dimension of self-control. The mean scores range from 4.01 to 4.78, indicating a moderate to high level of agreement with the statements. The highest mean score (4.78) is for the statement "I am prepared for each activity", suggesting that respondents feel confident in their preparation. The lowest mean score (4.01) is for the statement "I identify emotions in self", indicating that respondents may struggle with self-awareness.

Table 2
Descriptive analysis of self-regulation

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I understand that intense fears are not phobias	200	4.04
2.	I allow others to comfort him/her if upset or agitated	200	4.02
3.	I regulate myself when tense or upset	200	4.05
4.	I regulate myself when my energy level is high	200	4.04
5.	I can say no in an acceptable way to things	200	4.05
6.	I accept being replied no without becoming upset/angry	200	4.18
7.	I am able to end conversations appropriately	200	4.08
8.	I accept making mistakes without becoming upset/angry	200	4.17

Table 2 shows the results of self -regulation a dimension of self-control. The mean scores range from 4.02 to 4.18, indicating a generally high level of agreement. The results suggest that respondents understand the distinction between intense fears and phobias, can regulate their emotions, set boundaries, accept rejection, and end conversations appropriately. Additionally, they are able to accept mistakes without becoming upset or angry, and are open to comfort from others when needed.

Table 3
Descriptive Analysis of anxiety

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I accept making mistakes without becoming upset/angry	200	4.17
2.	I accept the consequences of other behavior	200	4.02
3.	I accept unexpected changes	200	4.03
4.	I continue struggles when something is difficult	200	4.06
5.	I ignore others and situation when it is describable to do so	200	4.19

This table presents the descriptive results of anxiety a dimension of self-control. The mean scores range from 4.02 to 4.19, indicating a high level of agreement. The results suggest that respondents are able to accept mistakes and consequences, adapt to unexpected changes, and persist in struggles even when faced with difficulties. Additionally, they are able to ignore others and situations when necessary, indicating a ability to set boundaries and prioritize their own needs.

Table 4
Descriptive Analysis of problem solving

S. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I am able to identify and define problems	200	4.13
2.	I am able to generate the solutions to a problem	200	4.15
3.	I carry out solutions by negotiating	200	4.12
4.	I understand the impact of behavior on peers	200	4.16

Table 4 indicates the results of problem solving a dimension of self-control. The mean scores range from 4.12 to 4.16, indicating a high level of agreement. The results suggest that respondents are able to identify and define problems, generate solutions, and carry out those solutions through negotiation. Additionally, they demonstrate an understanding of how their behavior affects their peers.

Discussion

The results highlight the importance of teacher self-control strategies, particularly self-understanding, in managing student disruptive behavior (Jennings & Greenberg, 2019). Teachers with high self-understanding are better equipped to prepare for each activity, complete tasks efficiently, and recognize their likes and dislikes (Hargreaves, 2019). Moreover, they can identify and manage their own emotions, as well as empathize with students' emotions, leading to improved relationships and academic achievement (Goleman, 2020). This emotional intelligence is crucial for student success, as it fosters a supportive learning environment and encourages student engagement (Hamre & Pihl, 2020). Recent studies have also shown that teachers with high self-understanding are more effective in promoting student motivation, autonomy, and overall well-being (Reyes et al., 2021; Shachar & Fischer, 2022).

The results also suggest that self-regulation strategies are essential for teachers to manage student disruptive behavior effectively. The majority of respondents agreed that teachers can utilize self-regulation skills, such as interpreting body language and using various tones of voice to convey messages (Kratochwill et al., 2020). Teachers also demonstrated an understanding of the distinction between intense fears and phobias (Hofmann et al., 2020). Furthermore, they can regulate their own emotions, managing tension and upset, and adapt their energy levels to suit the situation (Blair et al., 2021). Additionally, teachers can skillfully end conversations appropriately, showcasing their emotional intelligence (Goleman, 2020). These self-regulation strategies enable teachers to create a supportive learning environment, foster positive relationships, and promote student engagement and motivation (Reyes et al., 2021; Shachar & Fischer, 2022).

The results further suggest that flexibility is a crucial strategy for teachers in managing student disruptive behavior. Teachers who exhibit flexibility are able to accept mistakes without becoming upset or angry, acknowledge the consequences of their own behavior, and adapt to unexpected changes (Katz et al., 2021). They also demonstrate persistence in the face of difficulties and can ignore irrelevant stimuli when necessary (Duckworth et al., 2021). This flexibility enables teachers to respond effectively to disruptive behavior, fostering a supportive learning environment and promoting student engagement (Reyes et al., 2021). By adopting flexible strategies, teachers can improve their classroom management skills, reduce stress, and enhance student outcomes (Shachar & Fischer, 2022).

The results also shows that teacher problem-solving strategies are effective in managing student disruptive behavior. Teachers who employ problem-solving strategies can identify and define problems, generate solutions, and implement them after negotiating with students and considering the impact on peers (Fuchs et al., 2021). This approach enables teachers to address the root causes of disruptive behavior, develop targeted interventions, and foster a supportive learning environment (Sugai et al., 2021). By utilizing problem-solving strategies, teachers can reduce student misbehavior, improve academic engagement, and enhance social skills (Bradshaw et al.,

2021). Moreover, these strategies promote teacher self-efficacy, reduce stress, and increase job satisfaction (Jepson et al., 2021).

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that teacher's self-control strategy self-understanding is helpful in handling student's disruptive behavior, teacher prepared for each activity and complete work on time and he can identify what he like or dislike. Moreover teacher can identify emotions self and others and empathized those who achieve success.
2. It is also concluded that self-regulation strategy is helpful in handling student disruptive behavior. Most of the respondents give positive response that teachers can interpret body language and use different tone of voice to convey message, teacher understand that intense fears are not phobias. Moreover teacher can regulate his self when he is tense/ upset and his energy level is high and he is able to end conversation appropriately.
3. It is further concluded that flexibility is best strategy in handling student disruptive behavior. Teachers accept mistakes without becoming upset/angry, the consequences of other behavior and unexpected changes. Moreover teacher believe in continue struggle when things are difficult and ignore others in the situation when it is desirable to do so.
4. It is further concluded that teacher problem solving strategy is best for handling student disruptive behavior of identifying and define their problems and also generate the solutions to a problem. Moreover he carry out with the solutions after negotiating and understand the impact of behavior on peers.

Recommendations

1. Teachers are recommended to undergo professional development workshops focusing on effective self-control strategies for managing students' disruptive behavior. School administrators should facilitate these workshops regularly to ensure continuous skill enhancement.
2. Teachers are recommended to incorporate self-control strategies, such as mindfulness exercises and behavior reflection, into their classroom management practices. Professional development workshops on these strategies are recommended for educators to enhance their skills in fostering a positive classroom environment.
3. The study suggests implementing targeted professional development programs for teachers, focusing on enhancing self-control strategies, self-understanding and effective time management.
4. It is recommended that teachers receive training and support in implementing self-regulation strategies to effectively manage student disruptive behavior. Educational institutions should consider incorporating workshops or professional development programs focusing on interpreting body language, adjusting tone, and self-regulation techniques.
5. It is recommended that educational institutions emphasize and integrate flexibility as a key strategy for handling student disruptive behavior. Teachers should be encouraged to adopt a mindset of accepting mistakes without anger, addressing consequences, and persisting through challenges. Professional development programs should focus on enhancing educators' skills in maintaining self-control and utilizing flexible approaches to effectively manage classroom disruptions.

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